

Development of the serious game *Puff* for respiratory control during anxiety episodes in children

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Abstract— Anxiety is the most prevalent psychological disorder in childhood, often manifesting through symptoms such as muscle tension, gastrointestinal discomfort, and, most notably, impaired breathing regulation (e.g., rapid or shallow breathing). Effectively addressing these symptoms is essential to preserving children’s overall well-being and quality of life. Recent studies have shown that serious games can enhance adherence to respiratory therapies by transforming repetitive exercises into interactive, enjoyable experiences. In this context, the present study introduces the development of a serious game specifically designed to support anxiety management in children through the application of the 4-7-8 breathing technique. The game combines the use of a custom-built, additively manufactured breathing device with an immersive digital environment developed in the *Unity* platform. Altogether, this solution has potential to be an innovative, engaging, and effective tool for respiratory rehabilitation and emotional regulation in children. To confirm its applicability and therapeutic value, future work should involve controlled studies with pediatric participants.

Keywords — Pediatric Anxiety, Serious Games, Respiratory Therapy, Additive Manufacturing, Unity.

I. Introduction

Anxiety is a natural physiological response of the body, characterized by feelings of apprehension and alertness in the face of potentially threatening situations. However, when this reaction increases in intensity and frequency, significantly affecting daily activities, it constitutes a pathological anxiety disorder. Its manifestations include both cognitive symptoms (e.g., insecurity and irritability) and physical symptoms (e.g., tachycardia, gastrointestinal disturbances, and especially dyspnea) [1]. This condition is not limited to adulthood. It is estimated that 8% to 12% of children exhibit clinically relevant anxiety symptoms, with negative impacts on their development and academic performance [2]. In this context, alongside pharmacological treatments, non-pharmacological interventions have also gained prominence, particularly breathing regulation techniques, such as the 4-7-8 method (inhalation for 4 seconds, breath hold for 7, and exhalation for 8 seconds). The effectiveness of this technique is

supported both as a primary and adjunctive therapy [3, 4]. In parallel, within the scope of treatment and rehabilitation, the use of games has gained considerable space and adherence. Serious games have emerged as promising tools in rehabilitation, combining playful engagement with effectiveness comparable to traditional exercises. In other words, serious games have been widely explored in the literature as tools for treating respiratory comorbidities, showing potential in both pulmonary rehabilitation and the management of chronic conditions [5, 6]. Some approaches include mobile games that simulate environments for training specific breathing patterns, yielding significant improvements in lung capacity and reduced symptoms [7]. Others, with more playful platforms, have also been tested with children, combining interactive narratives with breathing control exercises, turning conventional therapies into more engaging experiences [8]. These interventions positively impact patients’ quality of life, suggesting that gamification may be a promising strategy in clinical practice. Given this, the present study proposes the development of a serious game focused on breathing control in children with anxiety, aiming to provide an intuitive and motivating interface for training breathing techniques. In addition, a mobile breathing device created through additive manufacturing is presented as an interesting and innovative solution to help reduce therapeutic adherence barriers in the pediatric population.

II. Methods

A. Selection and Gamification of the Breathing Protocol

Among the various respiratory therapy protocols identified in the literature, the 4-7-8 breathing technique was selected [4] due to its specific development for managing anxiety disorders. In this method, the individual inhales for four seconds, holds their breath for seven seconds, and exhales for eight seconds [9]. This controlled breathing pattern is designed to alleviate anxiety symptoms, such as headaches, sleep disturbances, and physiological dysregulation, while also contributing to improvements in heart rate, blood pressure, concentration, and focus.

To enhance engagement and treatment adherence among children, the game's storyline was crafted to provide a playful and immersive experience. The stages of the 4-7-8 breathing cycle were seamlessly integrated into key moments of the main character's journey. The player accompanies a bear on an adventure to reach the top of a mountain, where a party hosted by an owl awaits. Throughout the game, each stage of the breathing technique corresponds to a specific in-game activity:

- In the first stage, the player must assist the bear in inflating a bicycle's tires using their breathing. This action initiates the journey and is illustrated in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Initial stage of the game.

- In the next stage, the player assists the bear in inflating a football, which will be taken as a present to the owl's party. This stage is depicted in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Intermediate stage of the game.

- Finally, the player must inflate a balloon to enable the bear to reach the top of the mountain and, consequently, attend the owl's party. This stage is illustrated in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Final stage of the game.

B. Respiratory Flow Measurement System

To accurately capture the inhalation and exhalation movements, an Arduino Uno board was paired with the MPS20N0040D-D pressure sensor module. This module combines a pressure sensor that provides an analogue signal proportional to the pressure detected on its surface, with an HX710B analogue-to-digital converter (ADC) that digitises this signal. This setup enhances measurement precision and simplifies data processing within the graphical interface.

The sensor's four pins were soldered onto individual jumpers and connected to the Arduino as follows: the

VCC pin to the 5V power supply, the GND pin to ground, the OUT pin—which transmits the sensor's readings—to one of the analogue inputs, and the CLK pin—which synchronises digital data transfer from the module to the microcontroller—to a PWM input.

Once the electronic components were defined, the focus shifted to designing an air chamber to house the sensor module's inlet.

The initial prototype was a bottle-shaped chamber, designed to accommodate an average human breath volume of approximately 500 ml. However, this shape proved ergonomically impractical. The second design adopted a spherical form, significantly improving comfort during use. Yet, as the game demands deep breathing, the 500 ml volume fell short of the required respiratory flow capacity. Ultimately, the final model retained the spherical shape but increased the volume to 1 litre. Empirical testing confirmed this design to be well-suited for accurately measuring the respiratory flow necessary during gameplay.

Figure 4 visually depicts the development stages of the air receiving chamber.

Fig. 4. Evolution of the development of the air receiving chamber.

C. Hardware Framework

The framework to house the project's hardware system was developed, attached to the spherical air chamber, and manufactured using additive manufacturing with polylactic acid (PLA) filament. The device base, illustrated in Figure 5, was designed with a circular shape, based on the dimensions of the Arduino UNO board, and includes a side compartment sized to accommodate the USB cable used for serial connection.

Fig. 5. Base of the device and final placement of the Arduino board.

The base cover was designed to accommodate the jumpers connected to the Arduino and previously soldered to the pressure sensor module, through a hollow truncated segment

sized to fit the rectangular shape of the module. Figure 6 illustrates the final arrangement of the components and the device cover.

Fig. 6. Device top and final positioning of the pressure sensor.

Finally, the top of the structure was designed to allow the fitting of the sphere, which had its base manually drilled to 3 mm diameter, as shown in Figure 7, to accommodate the body of the pressure sensor, which has the same diameter. The drilling was performed manually to minimise potential printing errors caused by the small size.

Fig. 7. Drilling for integration of the air chamber with the sensor.

Figure 8 illustrates the completed device.

Fig. 8. Final layout of the project.

D. Graphical Interface

The game interface was developed using the Unity game development platform [10], which allowed customisation of the scenes and game elements, creating a more playful and immersive user experience. Initially, the main characters and interactive elements — namely, Puff the bear, the owl, the ball, the bicycle, and the balloon — were created using the Piskel application [11].

Figure 9 shows the game’s main menu screen, featuring options to start the game, adjust the background music volume—which was included to enhance the intended

therapeutic atmosphere, and, finally, an option to exit the application.

Fig. 9. Initial screen of the game, featuring buttons in Portuguese: Jogar (Play), Opções (Options), and Sair (Exit).

III. Results and Discussion

Following the project’s completion, the integration of the Graphical Interface with the Respiratory Measurement System resulted in the proposed Serious Game “Puff;” designed with children as the intended audience. The system has been implemented and tested for functionality, though it has not yet been evaluated with human participants.

The Serious Game “Puff” developed here differentiates itself from other existing devices in the literature through aspects such as the hardware employed, the respiratory measurement chamber, and its design focus on potential interaction with a young audience. Unlike other respiratory rehabilitation projects found in the literature [12], this project incorporates the barometric sensor module MPS20N0040D-D in its hardware setup, which is capable of measuring both positive and negative pressures. This allows the interface to detect both exhalation and inhalation within the system.

Additionally, the respiratory measurement chamber presents a unique approach compared to other devices described in the literature [13] by employing additive manufacturing as its fabrication method. This approach enables low-cost, scalable replication of the device, which could enhance accessibility in future testing. The Serious Game “Puff” also has potential to distinguish itself from others [14] by emphasizing design features intended to engage a child audience, such as a narrative centred on the bear’s movements, intended to give the game a playful character.

It is important to note that, at this stage, no experimental evaluation with pediatric patients has been conducted. Therefore, claims about engagement, enjoyment, or therapeutic effectiveness are not yet supported by data.

Nevertheless, this work has some limitations due to the absence of human testing, which precludes conclusions regarding user experience or therapeutic outcomes. Additional limitations include potential measurement precision and sensitivity constraints of the barometric sensor and the hardware setup.

IV. Conclusion

This work presented the design and implementation of the Serious Game “Puff” integrated with a respiratory measurement system. The prototype was successfully built and tested by the researchers for system functionality, including sensor detection of inhalation and exhalation, and the operation of the graphical interface. These results demonstrate that the proposed hardware and software components function as intended, forming a basis for further development.

At this stage, no experimental evaluation with users has been performed, so conclusions regarding engagement, usability, or therapeutic outcomes cannot be drawn. The project serves as a technical proof of concept and provides a foundation for future studies.

Future work will focus on experimental validation with human participants, improvements in interface usability, expansion of the game narrative, and enhancements to system connectivity, such as the addition of a Bluetooth module. These steps are essential to assess the practical applicability and potential benefits of the system for respiratory exercises in children.

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